

FORMATION OF CHOREOGRAPHIC SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific and theoretical importance of conducting choreography training in preschool educational institutions. Also, the possibilities of forming the intellectual skills of preschool children through choreography classes are highlighted.

Key words: Choreography, preschool educational organization, practical training, concept, music, theater, dance movements.

In the modern pedagogical process, there are trends indicating its unity, interaction, interpenetration of various components of the educational process, and renewal of the child's personality formation. The social demand of the society to educate the young generation of the 21st century is implemented within the framework of the humanistic concept of preschool education, which implies maximum support for the development of the child as a person and the development of children's activity. These are in academic and extracurricular activities. Preschool education is the initial socio-cultural formation of a child's personality, includes art as the main component of the educational process, is aimed at forming the child's aesthetic feelings to the real world, and children's artistic, practical and provides creative activity. in this field. Choreography is an effective means of learning and developing cultural heritage.

Syncretism of choreographic art implies the development of a sense of rhythm, the ability to hear and understand music, to coordinate movements with it, the muscle strength of the body and legs, the plasticity, elegance and expressiveness of hands. Dance lessons form the correct posture, inculcate the basics of etiquette and competent behavior in society, give an understanding of acting skills. Dance is of great importance in the realization of national identity. Thus, choreography has great potential for all-round aesthetic improvement of the child, his harmonious spiritual and physical development. The formation of choreographic skills is of particular importance in preschool age, when the foundations of a child's valuable attitude to the world are laid, the foundations of his personal culture are formed (*B.G. Ananiev, L.I. Bojovich, L.S. Vygotsky, A.V. Zaporozhets*).

The formation of choreographic skills in preschool children becomes a priority of pedagogical theory and practice at this stage of education, because it is at this age that the foundations of human culture are laid, interests, motivations and needs for systematic movement activities are formed. Dance is the richest source of aesthetic impressions of the child, forming his artistic "I" as an integral part of the "society" tool, through which he covers the most intimate and personal aspects of our existence into the sphere of social life.

Solving the problem of forming choreographic skills in preschool children can be done on the basis of a combination of positive motivation for choreographic activity, cultural compatibility, gender, multi-artistic, typological and participatory approaches. Communicative partnership and cooperation provide its methodological multilevel and hierarchical character due to situationality, tolerance, structural relations and conceptual

unity. The integration of these approaches has important theoretical and methodological potential for the formation of choreographic skills in preschool children and contributes to its updated forms, methods and content aspects. The main interrelated functions of the methodology of formation of choreographic skills of preschool children:

1. *Increasing* a stable interest in choreography based on the development of interest in culture, art history, and the surrounding world. At the heart of increasing sustained interest in choreography as one of the arts, it is necessary to protect the polyartistic approach that allows the child to understand the nature of dance in complex interaction with other art forms. Every child is initially polyartistic, because he has the ability to perceive different types of art. He perceives the world in the artistic images created in his fantasy and imagination. Everyone is capable of creating in any art.

Cultivating a stable interest in choreography is possible in the conditions of systematic work aimed at forming a system of ideas and knowledge about the diversity of dance art and its connection with other types (*visual, musical, theater, etc.*).

2. Educating universal human values in the process of choreography. The main principles of organizing the pedagogical process within the implementation of this function are as follows:

- ❖ *providing optimal emotional, cognitive and motor activity to each child;*
- ❖ *confidential communication, cooperative position towards children;*
- ❖ *to give each child the right to positive freedom in behavior and activity;*
- ❖ *the principle of ensuring children's success in organized cognitive and creative activities;*
- ❖ *the principle of taking into account the age and gender characteristics and capabilities of children when choosing methods of working with them.*

3. **Comprehensive** education of preschool children in the process of choreography. The basis of choreographic activity is dance, which is characterized by two components: spiritual and cultural (aesthetic) and physical. "*Dance lessons not only teach to understand and create beauty, but also develop imaginative thinking and fantasy, ensure harmonious plastic development.*" The multifunctional possibilities of dance allow all children to be involved in choreographic activities for their comprehensive and harmonious development. However, the importance of choreography in the modern system of preschool education is not sufficiently appreciated. This situation is related to the lack of scientific developments in the field of children's choreography. Only certain aspects of the problem were studied: the musical and rhythmic development of children, their involvement in creativity in dance activities, the use of national musical and choreographic traditions in the musical and motor development of preschool children, a polyartistic approach to mastering visual imagery. The nature of children's choreography or choreography is one of the auxiliary means of physical, mental, moral education of preschool children. There is no comprehensive technology for mass involvement of children in dance activities. At the same time, in our opinion, complex choreographic education technology is the most effective solution to the problem of formation of choreographic skills in preschool children.

The basis of teaching children with disabilities should be based on the beginning of play. Playing in a choreography class should not be a reward or a rest after hard work, on the contrary, work arises on the basis of play, becomes its content and continuation. As **E. Jacques-Dalcroze** said: "*Play develops individuality*". During the game, the child learns to repeat his impressions and ideas, therefore, the game is a powerful tool for strengthening the thinking ability and developing the mind.

Properly selected and organized dance games during the educational process contribute to the ability to work, arouse interest in lessons and work. In choreography classes for children with disabilities, it is necessary to use various musical games, games for orientation in space and types of rearrangement, games that develop memory. The specificity of choreography training is related to constant physical activity. But physical activity itself does not have an educational value for a child. It must be compatible with creativity, mental work and emotional expression. The main task is to instill in children a desire to express themselves creatively, master emotions, and understand beauty. Choreography is a component of working with children and their creative development. Thanks to the integrated approach, a creative, well-developed person is formed who can adapt to different life situations.

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